

PROTECTION OF HUMAN RIGHTS AND FREEDOMS IN THE VIEW OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This research aims to analyze the extent to which they are protected by law and the state, also provide an overview of human rights and freedoms.

Аннотация: Данное исследование направлено на анализ того насколько они защищены законом государством б а также дает обзор прав и свобод человека.

Key words: Human right, civil society, Constitution, independence, dignity, discrimination, violation of human rights, serious crime, self-management, holding referendums, democratic country, liberalization, judicial system.

In the every democratic country, human rights and freedom are defined as the first, the main issue. It plays a key role in the concept of deepening democratic reforms and developing civil society in our country, which was put forward by the head of our state . In Uzbekistan, the protection of human rights and freedoms has been a topic of significant focus and development in recent years. The government has taken steps to enhance human rights protections and has made efforts to align its practices with international standards. A number of political and social activities have been carried out in order to focus fairly on human rights and freedom. Including:

- consistent implementation of constitutional principles;
- strict control of powers of legislative and representative organs;
- further reform and liberalization of the judicial system;
- ensuring its independence;

- to organize a number of seminars for people to know their rights and freedom;
- educating the younger generation in the spirit of justice and humanity.

After Uzbekistan had obtained independence, within short historical period, the legal basis for the formation of national statehood was created, a strong democratic state by striving for the interests and well-being of the people was built. These were achieved with the selflessness, initiative, and enthusiasm of our first president Islom Abdiganievich Karimov, and today's new Uzbekistan is being achieved thanks to the leadership and initiative of our honorable president Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev in creating a strong and stable legal civil society. In fact, a clear example of this is the new Constitution of the new Uzbekistan, which came into force recently. It has a separate special section entitled “Fundamental rights, freedom, and duties of a person and a citizen”, which guarantees human rights and freedoms with these several articles.

In particular, Article 26 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that the dignity and worth of a person is inviolable. It is said that nothing can be the basis for discrimination against them.

During our lifetime, we are witnessing a lot of violence and violation of human rights, among which the oppression against women is very rampant. In order to prevent this, our state took women under its protection. That is, on April 11 of last year, a law was signed in Uzbekistan to ensure the protection of women and minors from violence. “From this day, we must emphasize that not only women but the state itself is against any form of violence. It is time to officially assess domestic violence as a serious crime”, said Saida Mirziyoyeva in her speech.

Moreover, citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan have political rights in addition to their personal civil, environmental, social, economic, cultural rights and freedoms. Uzbekistan citizen have the right to participate in the management of society and state affairs directly and through their representatives. Such participation is carried out through self-management, holding referendums and democratic formation of state bodies, as well as public control over the activities of state bodies.

Legislative reforms—Uzbekistan has implemented several legislative reforms aimed at safeguarding human rights. These reforms have addressed issues such as torture, freedom of speech, assembly, and religion.

Judicial reforms – the Uzbek government has been working on improving the independence and effectiveness of the judiciary. Efforts to ensure a fair trial, combat corruption within the legal system, and strengthen the rule of law have been part of the broader agenda to protect human rights.

Civil society engagement—There has been an increase in civil society engagement in Uzbekistan, with the government allowing more space for non-governmental organizations and human rights defenders to operate.

Media freedom – there have been developments in the realm of media freedom in Uzbekistan, with increased opportunities for independent journalism and the relaxation of restrictions on media sector have contributed to a more open environment for the free flow of information.

International cooperation – Uzbekistan has engaged in partnerships with international organizations and foreign governments to strengthen human rights protections. Collaboration with entities such as the United Nations and the European Union has supported Uzbekistan’s efforts to align its human rights practices with global standards.

While progress has been made in advancing human rights and freedoms in Uzbekistan, challenges remain, including the need for further reforms, ensuring consistent enforcements of law, and addressing specific human rights issues effectively. Continued efforts to enhance and promote a culture of respect for human dignity are vital for the ongoing development of Uzbekistan’s human rights landscape.

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